

been screened, including internationally known cold-tolerant checks Stejaree 45, Akiyudaka, China 1039, Palung 2, Fuji 102, and Phalame.) Leaf color, panicle exsertion, spikelet sterility, and yield parameters were scored visually at seedling, booting, anthesis, and maturity stages.

Above 1,400 m, most of the exotic varieties either failed to produce panicles or produced degenerated spikelets with a high degree of sterility. Yield performance of indigenous cultivars was reliable above 1,300 m (Fig. 2). At 1,500 m altitude, local variety Chhomro outyielded all other varieties; at 2,000 m, its performance was outstanding. This variety demonstrated an ability to tolerate

chilling at different growth stages at all altitudes.

The National Variety Releasing Board has released Chhomro as Chhomrong dhan, the first indigenous variety for areas above 1,400 m asl. It also has been included as a cold-tolerant entry in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery and LRARC's chilling-tolerant rice breeding program. Results on segregating materials resulting from crosses between Chhomrong and exotic cold-tolerant lines are very promising.

Identification in recent years of Chhomrong dhan and several other varieties suitable for the low to high hills of Nepal has confirmed the value of field screening at different altitudes. □

Grain yield (t/ha) at 12% moisture content

2. Yield of Chhomro and mean yields of NRCTN across altitudes, 1987-88.

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Response of some rice cultivars to lime application on acid sulfate soils

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We studied the effect of lime on rice cultivar yields in acid sulfate soils at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, during the 1989 dry season (Table 1).

In split-plot design with three replications, four lime levels (0, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 t/ha) were the main plot treatments and five rice cultivars (BW267-3, CR261-

7039-236, IR6023-10-1-1, Kapuas, and IR26) were subplot treatments. Lime was applied 15 d before transplanting. Three 21-d-old seedlings/hill were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 4- × 5-m plots. At transplanting, we fertilized the rice basally with 90 kg N/ha, 26.4 kg P/ha, and 41.5 kg K/ha.

Yields in plots with 2.0 t lime/ha were significantly higher than those at other levels (Table 2).

In the cultivar treatments, Kapuas and BW267-3 yielded significantly higher than other varieties. In general, yield increased as lime was added. □

Table 2. Effect of lime on yield of rice cultivars in acid sulfate soils at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, 1989 dry season.

Lime (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	BW267-3	CR261-7039-236	IR6023-10-1-1	Kapuas	IR26
0	1.7	1.4	1.4	1.7	1.3
0.5	2.1	1.5	1.5	2.1	1.4
1.0	2.1	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.0
2.0	2.6	1.7	2.1	2.6	2.2
Mean	2.1	1.6	1.8	2.1	1.7

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of acid sulfate soil at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

	0-20 cm deep	20-40 cm deep
pH (H ₂ O)	3.95	3.90
Total N (%)	0.41	0.19
Organic C (%)	2.78	1.70
Available P (ppm)	17.63	32.96
Exchangeable K (meq/100g)	0.19	0.13
SO ₄ (%)	0.12	0.05
Al ³⁺ (meq/100g)	14.19	15.70
Na (meq/100 g)	0.12	0.26
Fe ³⁺ (meq/100 g)	6.16	5.59
Particle size (%)		
Sand	0.22	0.21
Silt	33.41	31.14
Clay	66.37	68.65

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

New rice cultivar Marianna obtained through anther culture

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Marianna is a new short-stemmed, lodging-resistant rice cultivar.

It is a dihaploid line, obtained from a 1983 F₁ hybrid combination Belozem/Plovdiv 22 through anther culture.

We tested Marianna alone and with other cultivars until 1986. From 1986 to 1989, it was tested in some regular trials at State Cultivar Commission stations. It was acknowledged as an original cultivar at the commission's 45th plenary session.

Marianna is related to the japonica rices. Its vegetative phase is 121-125 d,